

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Atlantic Region (Spain)

PROBLEM

What are the most commonly used agroecological methods for weed control in vineyards in the Atlantic Region?

STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS

Among surveyed farmers, stakeholders, and cocreation workshop participants, mowing is the most frequently used method for weed control in vineyards (82%), followed by tillage (68%) and spontaneous cover (42%). Inert mulching, living mulching, and both permanent and temporary cover crops are applied by 32% of respondents. Mechanical weed management and hand weeding are also well-known and practiced. Grazing, bioherbicides, and thermal weed control are much less common (5%). Despite this, these techniques, along with mixed cropping and cover crops with various species, were recommended in workshops as valuable options for enhancing agroecological weed control. Some stakeholders suggested the potential of bioherbicides and thermal weed control, but these remain underutilized. There is a strong interest in integrating diverse practices, such as spontaneous weed cover within rows and cover cropping between rows, to manage weeds effectively. However, lack of knowledge and practical training on these strategies remains a barrier to wider adoption.

Figure 1: Vineyard where agroecological strategies for weed management are being tested

RECOMMENDATION

A combined approach utilizing mowing, diverse cover crops, and mulching is recommended for effective weed management in vineyards. Training and awareness programs should focus on underutilized methods such as bioherbicides and thermal weed control to improve adoption. Emphasizing these practices can enhance weed control, improve soil health, and contribute to more sustainable vineyard management in the Atlantic region.

KEYWORDS

mowing, tillage, spontaneous cover, AS combined approach, sustainability

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